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**Numerical simulations of fluctuations of the thermocline
forced with synoptic data for wind and pressure**

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Abstract

The second largest gas field in Norway, Ormen Lange, is located at Storegga 140 km west of Kristiansund. Ormen Lange lies in the continental shelf slope where several slides have created a rough bottom topography.

Measurements at Ormen Lange and Svinøy have revealed events with a drop in temperature and peak values in speed over a short period of time. Some of these events are believed to be caused by travelling atmospheric low pressure systems. Two of the most significant events in the year 2000 are selected for model runs. A three-dimensional, time split, σ -coordinate model is used for the simulations. The model is forced with synoptic atmospheric data, ie. sea level pressure and wind velocities 10 m above surface.

Comparisons of model results and observations show that the fluctuations in temperature are much larger in the observations than in the model results. The atmospheric pressure gradients are generally weak and they may not be strong enough to force the observed oscillations with the applied background stratification. This means that the main forcing mechanism behind the large observed fluctuations, is not the atmospheric forcing from this period alone.

The main explanation for the discrepancy is probably unrealistically smooth initial values of salinity and temperature. In lack of synoptic data of these fields from the model period, climatological data sets have been used as initial values. These data sets are generally smooth as they represent mean values over time, and internal fronts are weak. In reality, such fronts may be very strong at Ormen Lange. The transition zone from Atlantic Water and Norwegian Sea Intermediate Water may be only 20-40 m thick. As such fronts pass a measurement station, large jumps in temperature are observed, and, associated with these rapid changes in temperature, large current velocities are often measured.

This also supports the conclusion; to capture main events correctly in space and time, it is necessary to have sufficient measurements of salinity and temperature to force the model, in addition to the atmospheric forcing.

1 Introduction

Ormen Lange is the second largest gas field in Norway and is located in the Storegga region approximately 130 km offshore of mid-Norway. The depth varies between 800 and 1100 m. This is the first deep water hydrocarbon project outside the Norwegian shelf.

Ormen Lange lies in the core of an area where several submarine slides have taken place. This means that a steep head wall is left and the seabed below is covered with high escarpments and local sea mounts. Such extreme topography may generate focusing and blocking effects on the currents. Internal waves may also be generated by these obstacles. These effects are, at the moment, poorly resolved by thermohaline circulation models.

Both the rough topography and the high current speed in this area may cause problems for near seabed installations needed for developing, producing and transporting the gas from the field. It is therefore important to understand the phenomena acting at Ormen Lange and their driving forces before the developing of the gas field begins.

An ongoing data acquisition program in the area has identified several events, in which the currents close to the seabed exhibit peak values in their speed and temperature over a short period of time. Earlier reports (Eliassen et al. 2000) have commented on these events and suggested two plausible explanations for the high current speeds occurring at Ormen Lange; internal waves that break towards the shelf slope or currents at strong internal density fronts. The most pronounced generation mechanism behind internal wave phenomena in this area is believed to be atmospheric forcing, Vikebø et al. (2001). Numerical experiments with idealised travelling low pressures, Vikebø et al. (2001), have supported that near seabed events with peak values in temperature and speed can be driven by atmospheric forcing.

Svinøy is located about 70 km south-west of Ormen Lange. The bottom topography in this area is more gentle, with a smoother slope than in the Ormen Lange area. At Svinøy there has been a monitoring program ongoing since April 1995. This data can produce valuable information together with the data from Ormen Lange, about the movement of fronts and internal waves along the Norwegian shelf. This information, gathered by examining the recordings of temperature at moorings located at same depth (in same water masses), see Table 2, will then be compared with numerical model results.

In the eastern part of the Norwegian sea, there are four different water masses. See Figure 1. These water masses are determined by the salinity and the temperature given in Table 1. The measurements in this report from Ormen Lange and Svinøy show that under the events, Norwegian Sea Arctic

Figure 1: The water masses at the Norwegian shelf and shelf slope. Norwegian Coastal Water (NCW), Atlantic Water (AW), Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water (NSAIW) and Norwegian Sea Deep Water (NSDW).

Intermediate Water masses are displacing the Atlantic Water masses that are usually located at the mooring depth.

Synoptic atmospheric data is used as external force in the numeric model. Two time periods, 20-30/6-2000 and 4-14/11-2000, are simulated. Recordings at Ormen Lange and Svinøy have revealed a significant drop in temperature for these periods, see Figure 2. Similar for these periods are atmospheric cyclones in the northern North Atlantic extending toward West-Norway prior to the cold water upwelling. Following are periods with relatively low pressure over Southern Norway compared to the Norwegian Sea. The observed temperature drops are preceded by a strong north-easterly wind, Skagseth (2002).

Figures of velocity, salinity and temperature from the model, 20 m above the seabed, will be presented at the locations indicated in Figure 3 b) and compared with observations at the corresponding locations. The depths at the locations (modelled and measured) are given in Table 2.

2 Model

This model study uses the numerical σ -coordinate ocean model of Berntsen (2000). The equations are the continuity equation for an incompressible fluid, the Reynold averaged hydrostatic momentum equations, conservation equations for temperature and salinity and the UNESCO-equation of state.

Figure 2: Measurements from Ormen Lange (bold line) and Svinøy (narrow line). Skagseth 2002

Layer	T (°C)	S (p.s.u)
NCW	$2.0 < T < 13.0$	$32.00 < S < 35.00$
AW	$T > 2.0$	$S > 35.00$
NSAIW	$-0.5 < T < 0.5$	$S < 34.90$
NSDW	$T < -0.5$	34.91

Table 1: Salinity and temperature of the layers in Figure 1

The reader is referred to Berntsen (2000) for further details concerning the governing equations and numerical methods.

The model area covers the south eastern part of the Norwegian Sea basin, (see Figure 3) with 4 km horizontal grid resolution. In the vertical, 30 σ -layers are applied and these are distributed according to a formula given in Lynch et al. (1995). The formula distributes the layers symmetrically about the midpoint in the vertical with a gradually finer resolution towards the surface and the bottom.

The model is run 240 and 288 hours (the June and November event) with an internal 3-D time step of 120 s. There are 30 2-D time steps per 3-D step. Initial values of water elevation, velocities, temperature and salinity from

Location (20 m abs)	Mooring depth	Model depth
OL (OL8)	458	456
SV (SV1)	470	462

Table 2: Depths in meters for the locations in this report.

Figure 3: Bottom topography from the model runs. The grid size is 4 km.

Eldevik et al. (2001), are interpolated from 20 km into 4 km grid resolution. These are climatological values that have been spun up over a period of 165 days. The spin up process sharpens the density gradients in the model to some extent.

At the lateral open boundaries, a flow relaxation scheme (FRS) is implemented (Martinsen and Engedahl, 1987). The FRS-zones are 7 grid-cells wide. In addition to the initial values for water elevation (η), velocity (u and v), temperature (T) and salinity (S), four tidal constituents (M_2 , S_2 , K_1 , N_2), are used to specify the lateral boundary conditions.

The real atmospheric forcing fields used in these simulations are from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). The resolution of the atmospheric forcing fields are given in $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ lat/long with 6-hour time intervals. To correctly distribute the atmospheric forcing fields, bilinear interpolation in space and quasi-hermite interpolation in time are performed.

The model is at first run with no atmospheric forcing present in 24 hours. Then a time period of 12 hours where the atmospheric forcing is linearly increased toward the ECMWF data. This is done to avoid that transients from the start-up phase propagate into the time interval of interest. For

the remaining simulation time, the ECMWF forcing fields are used. This start-up is done with introducing a forcing factor (FF) formula,

$$FF = \begin{cases} 0 & 0 - 24 h \\ \frac{TIME-24}{12} & 24 - 36 h \\ 1 & 36 - \rightarrow h \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where $TIME$ is the model time in hours.

Wind velocities 10 m above sea surface and the sea level pressure can then be found by

$$[u, v]_{ATM} = FF \cdot [u, v]_{ECMWF} \quad (2)$$

$$P_{ATM} = (P_{ECMWF} - P_{MEAN}) \cdot FF + P_{MEAN} \quad (3)$$

where the subscript ATM is used as the forcing field in the model, $ECMWF$ is the interpolated $ECMWF$ data and $P_{MEAN} = 101300$ Pa is the mean sea level pressure in the model.

From the wind velocity, wind stress is computed

$$\tau_x = \rho_a c_D (u_{ATM}^2 + v_{ATM}^2)^{1/2} u_{ATM} \quad , \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_y = \rho_a c_D (u_{ATM}^2 + v_{ATM}^2)^{1/2} v_{ATM} \quad , \quad (5)$$

where c_D is the drag coefficient. In our experiments c_D is chosen to be 3×10^{-3} (cf. Martinsen et al. 1979).

The bottom topography (Figure 3 a)) is taken from the ETOPO5 data set, 5 min long and lat, (Data announcement 88-MGG-02, Digital relief of the Surface of the Earth, NOAA, National Geophysical Data Center, Boulder, Colorado, 1988) and interpolated (bilinear) into 4 km grid resolution. A more realistic topography is inserted for the Ormen Lange area.

3 Model results

The June event:

Figure 4 a) shows a weak decrease in temperature in the beginning of the period for Svinøy, then a weak increase starting around the 26 of June lasting three days. For Ormen Lange there are strong oscillations from the 24 of June throughout the period. For the first three days the temperature is increasing followed by decreasing temperature the next three days. At the end of this period there is a weak decrease in temperature at Ormen Lange.

Comparing the measurements (Figure 2 a)) and the model result (Figure 4 a)) show that the model has not been able to recapture the measured

(a) Time period 20-30/6 2000.

(b) Time period 2-14/11 2000.

Figure 4: Model result. Temperature in degrees at Ormen Lange (bold line) and Svinøy (narrow line).

dramatic drop in temperature from the time period 20-30 June 2000. But still there are some resemblances between the model and the measured data. For Svinøy, the bottom of the drop from the model is located between 23-27 of June which corresponds to the measured data. For Ormen Lange both the model and the measured data show a stronger variability.

In Vikebø et al. 2001 connections between the strength of the travelling low pressure and the magnitude of the currents and the change in temperature were discussed. One of the conclusions was that the strong passing lows gave stronger currents and greater temperature changes than weaker lows. Thiem et al. 2002 showed that a travelling low would give a down-welling situation (increase in temperature) if the low passed north of the area. There will be an up-welling situation (decrease in temperature) if the low passed south of the area. Based on this, there should be a major low pressure entering south of Svinøy and Ormen Lange between 23-25 June, if this event is caused by a local travelling low pressure.

From Figure 5 we see that there is no strong travelling low pressure system passing south of Ormen Lange and Svinøy. For most of this period a weak low pressure is located in the southern part of Norway/Sweden giving wind from north. It is therefore not likely that this low pressure created the event measured at Svinøy and Ormen Lange in the period 20-30 June 2000.

Figure 5: Mean sea level pressure fields in millibars at daily intervals from 22 to 27 June 2000. Skagseth (2002).

Figure 6: Mean sea level pressure fields in millibars at daily intervals from 4 to 9 November 2000. Skagseth (2002).

The November event:

The model results are similar to the results for June. For Svinøy there is a decrease in the temperature the first five-six days, followed by an increase that lasts two-three days. At Ormen Lange it starts with an increase in the mean temperature the first three days followed by a weak decrease in the mean temperature. The main difference between the two time series is, however, that the oscillations at Ormen Lange are much stronger than at Svinøy.

The comparison between the measured data in Figure 2 b) and the result from the model (Figure 4 b)) show that the strong drop in temperature is not reproduced by the model. The model gives a minimum value between 6-8 November, while the measurements has the minimum value between 9-11 November. There is a low-pressure located outside the north-western part of south Norway at the beginning of the period, see Figure 6. This low-pressure is then reduced and a new low-pressure enters the northern part of Great Britain. Both these two low-pressures have a significant pressure deviation from the mean pressure. The first one has a large extent, which makes the pressure gradient relatively weak. This can explain that the measurements in Figure 2 b) do not show a local event at Svinøy and Ormen Lange early in this period. The low-pressure later in the period located over the northern part of Great Britain is mainly outside the model domain, and is therefore not represented in the model.

From the model results for these two time periods (Figure 4) there are similarities. They both show a drop in temperature over the same time interval in the beginning of the period, and an increase afterwards. This can indicate that this drop in temperature is driven mainly by the initial conditions for temperature and salinity and not from the atmospheric forcing.

If these events are not due to low-pressure activity in the Norwegian Sea, then we need to seek for other solutions.

A period with wind from the south will result in a down-welling of Atlantic Water, which pushes the thermocline down. If this period is followed by a change in the wind direction or magnitude this may cause a sudden drop in the temperature when the displaced water flows back into its initial position. This seems actually to be the case in the beginning of the June period, but it is doubtful that the amplitude of the isotherm generated from the weak low-pressure in southern Norway is large enough to displace the Atlantic Water for several days, as the measurements indicate.

This leaves a more probable explanation. An internal travelling density

(a) Along the line Svinøy-Ormen Lange.

(b) Angle between the line Svinøy-Ormen Lange.

Figure 7: The direction of the propagation of internal density fronts.

front that enters the area. Such an internal density front can be set up by a strong low pressure in a continental slope region, or by a disturbance in the deep water circulation or thermohaline circulation. This can happen in areas far from the Norwegian shelf and the front can travel toward the area where the measurements are done. The sudden and strong drop in temperature in the June event may be due to the passage of an internal front.

An internal density front usually propagates quite slow due to the reduced gravity. The distance between Svinøy and Ormen Lange is ≈ 70 km and Figure 2 a) shows that the time lag between the front appearing at Svinøy and Ormen Lange is ≈ 1.3 days. Assuming that the front moves in a straight line with constant speed this gives a maximum speed of 0.6 m/s. This is shown in Figure 7 a). If the crest of the front and the straight line between Svinøy and Ormen Lange intersects at an angle other than 90° , the front moves slower, see Figure 7 b).

If the June event is due to a travelling density front, Figure 2 a) indicates that this front can propagate over days without losing its shape.

As Figure 1 shows, the water in this area can be divided into four different layers. Each layer has small changes in density, and there is a jump in density on the interface between the layers. Measurements from Ormen Lange of the

water masses show that this transition zone between the layers can be only 20-50 m thick, see Figure 8. The front is a vertical movement of the interface between the layers. The models initial conditions for salt and temperature are taken from spun up climatological values, which are known to be smooth. This means that there are no strong gradients present in the model, as can be found in the Norwegian Sea. The rapid change in temperature measured in Figure 2 a) can therefore be set up by a relatively small vertical movement compared to the vertical movement the model must set up in order to give the same change in temperature.

To understand which forces are of most importance at Svinøy and Ormen Lange some numerical simulations for the period 2-10 November 2000 have been done. These simulations have been run with tidal and atmospheric forcing combined, tidal forcing alone and without any of these forces. Figure 9 shows the the different scenarios and which effect they have on the movement of the isotherms at Svinøy and Ormen Lange.

Svinøy:

When the wind forcing is present, it results in an increase in the amplitude of the fluctuation of the isotherms. The effect is strongest for the time period 5-8 November. This is the time interval where the temperature drop in the measured data occurs. At the end of this period (8-10 November) the amplitude is approximately the same for the fluctuations for simulations only with tide and simulations including both tide and atmospheric forcing.

For the simulation where there are no tidal forces present, the decrease in temperature the first two days, and the increase after the 7'th day, has the same magnitude as when tidal forces are present in the simulation.

Ormen Lange:

Also for Ormen Lange there is an increase in amplitude when there is wind forcing present. But the most interesting feature is the strong oscillations, which are damped and changes the period when the tidal forcing is turned off. This indicates that the oscillations seen at Ormen Lange are forced by the tide. The period on these oscillations is almost 12 h. This means that the diurnal tidal constituent is the most dominating on the oscillations in this area.

Figure 9 shows that there will be an increase in the oscillations and the maximum value at the isotherms when atmospheric forcing is present. But the initial conditions for salinity and temperature will in this case give a increase or decrease in temperature, independent on the other forces that are acting.

Figure 8: Vertical profiles of recorded hydrography 4-5 April 2000. From Current Measurements at Ormen Lange, Data report no. 2. Oceanor.

(a) Wind and tide.

(b) Tide.

(c) No wind and no tide.

Figure 9: Model result 2-10 November 2000. Temperature in degrees at Ormen Lange (bold line) and Svinøy (narrow line).

4 Discussion

The events with a sudden drop in temperature measured at the given locations, at Ormen Lange and Svinøy, are connected to displacements vertical and/or horizontal of the interface between Atlantic Water and Norwegian Sea Arctic Intermediate Water. Usually, both the locations considered in this report lie in the Atlantic Water. When an event occurs, the Atlantic Water masses are displaced by the much colder Norwegian Arctic Intermediate Water which causes a drop in the temperature.

The synoptic atmosphere pressure gradients may force the movements of the interfaces between the water masses. However, the dynamics of this interface at a given time may also be due to fluxes of heat and/or momentum between the atmosphere and the ocean that occurred weeks or even months earlier. Such fluxes may for instance have generated large bodies of cold and heavy water masses in the Greenland Sea that move first southward, then eastward with the East Icelandic Current, before they hit areas of the slope close to Ormen Lange.

In this report synoptic data for sea level pressure and wind 10 m above sea surface is used to see if two of the major events in 2000 were due to the low pressure activity in this time period. The model results show that the low pressure activity increases the temperature drop, but then does not show that it is the low pressure that causes the drop. It is important to remember that this does not rule out low pressure activity as a generator of events at Ormen Lange or Svinøy, but for these two significant events it is not likely that it was a nearby low pressure that created them.

The two strong events in this report are therefore believed to be caused by an internal travelling density front. The problem with density fronts is that there is too little measured data to reveal where they come from and what has created them. Using initial conditions for salt and temperature from the climatology in lack of synoptic data can therefore not capture events connected to travelling internal density fronts. Predicting events caused by internal density fronts is therefore not possible without moorings surrounding the area of interest.

The numerical simulations show that Ormen Lange is more exposed to strong oscillations than Svinøy. This agrees with the measurements. The model also indicates that these oscillations are forced by the the diurnal tidal component.

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